

An azide-functionalized Al(III)-based metal-organic framework for the fast, selective and highly sensitive detection of exogenous and endogenous H₂S

Soutick Nandi,^a Helge Reinsch,^b Sooram Banesh,^c Norbert Stock,^b Vishal Trivedi,^c Shyam Biswas,^{*a}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, IIT Guwahati, 781039 Assam.

^bInstitut für Anorganische Chemie, Christian-Albrechts-Universität, Max-Eyth-Strasse 2, 24118 Kiel, Germany.

^cDepartment of Biosciences and Bioengineering, IIT Guwahati, 781039 Assam, India.

E-mail: sbiswas@iitg.ernet.in. Mob no: +91-8011097409

Abstract

MOFs, which are a new class of crystalline porous compounds, possess versatile application potentials ranging from gas storage/separation, chemical sensing and heterogeneous catalysis to biomedical imaging and drug delivery [1]. A new, azide-functionalized Al(III)-based metal-organic framework (MOF) denoted as CAU-10-N₃ (**1**, CAU = Christian-Albrechts-University) and consisting of 5-azido-isophthalic acid (H₂IPA-N₃) ligand was employed as a reaction-based fluorescent turn-on probe for the detection of H₂S. The activated compound (**1'**) showed fast, selective and highly sensitive sensing properties for extracellular H₂S in HEPES buffer. The limit of detection of **1'** for H₂S is 2.65 μM, which is lower than the earlier reports on MOFs for H₂S sensing. The material displayed short response time (420 s) and significant increase (20-fold) after 1 min of addition of Na₂S in the fluorescence intensity towards H₂S. Macrophage cells loaded with probe **1'** exhibited blue fluorescence with a response time of 15 min after Na₂S addition, indicating the suitability of the probe for intracellular H₂S detection.

Fig. 1. (a) Structure of the CAU-10-N₃ MOF. (b) Fluorescence turn-on response of the MOF suspension in HEPES buffer (10 mM, pH = 7.4) towards addition of Na₂S. (c) Ability of the MOF to detect H₂S in macrophage J774A.1 cells.

Keywords: metal-organic framework, azide-functionalization, fluorogenic probe, H₂S sensing, cell imaging.

References: [1] Themed issue on MOFs: *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2009**, *38*, 1201-1508.